

Pharmacology of select narcotic analgesics

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Abstract

Pain accompanies a human being from his birth until his death. It is associated with an unpleasant experience. There is a group of patients who can feel severe pain. In the 21st century no man should feel the pain connected with a disease process. Administration of opioids is the most effective method of relieving pain. The World Health Organization introduced rules for the treatment of pain based on the analgesic ladder, starting from non-opioid analgesics up to strong opioids. The division of opioids is based on their affinity for opioid receptors, which are located in different parts of the body. Morphine is the commonest analgesic drug used in emergency medicine. Acute pain caused by trauma, acute cardiac incidents and chronic pain are main recommendations on the morphine application. Adverse side effects of morphine include respiratory depression, which can lead to acute respiratory failure.

Keywords: pain, opioids, morphine, respiratory depression, analgesic ladder

Introduction

All substances derived by chemical means from the sap of unripe poppy heads of the opium poppy *Papaver somniferum* are called opiates. Opioids are classified as narcotic analgesics. They are the commonest drugs used in treatment of acute and chronic pain syndromes.[1]

An outline of the history of opioid administration seems to be interesting from the medical point of view. The opium poppy was cultivated with the aim of obtaining opium in Mesopotamia in prehistory. This practice caused poppy cultivation to spread to another countries. It is a fact that ancient Egyptians used opium as an analgesic in acute and chronic pains. Even in the 1st century B.C. Hippocrates described analgesic effect of the poppy juice. Friedrich Serturmer, German pharmacist, who isolated morphine alkaloid from opium in 1917, made an important milestone. At the turn of 19th and 20th centuries heroin was synthesised for the first time and administered as a cough medicine. Opioid receptors were discovered and classified in 1967.[2]

Mechanism of action

Pharmacologic effect of opioids closely associates with existence of specialised protein structures called receptors. The task of a receptor is to receive and transduce a piece of information, and to trigger a particular biological effect.

Receptors mu, kappa and delta are main types of opioid receptors.

It is an interesting detail that human organism is capable of secreting of endogenous opioids in the form of enkephalin, endorphin and dynorphin. Originally they are synthesised as an inactive precursor which gradually undergoes hydrolysis.[3]

Opioids have a broad spectrum of action depending on their different pharmacodynamic properties or the type of activated opioid receptor. The site of opioid administration also affects analgesic effect.[3]

Central mechanism of analgesic effect produced by opioids concerns anatomical location of pain centres in the brain. Małgorzata Krajnik and Zbigniew Żylicz show that one particular centre responsible for analgesia does not exist. They claim that the largest centres can be found

in the midbrain, namely in periaqueductal grey matter, and in the ventrocaudal part of the medulla oblongata.[3] Each narcotic analgesic acts in stages on the level of the medulla. Its action can be heterogenous depending on diversity of activated opioid receptors. During morphine administration activation of receptors mu, kappa and delta occurs followed by releasing neurotransmitters, which influences on analgesic effect and evokes side effects.[3]

Narcotic analgesics may also act peripherally. It concerns the occurrence of opioid receptors not only on the endings of nervous C fibers, but also in tissues with a local inflammatory reaction. Exogenous opioids administered locally have anti-inflammatory effect and reveal more long-lasting analgesic effect compared with their parenteral administration.[4]

The means of administration of analgesic drugs is of pharmacodynamic importance and it determines the effect of analgesic drugs on the organism. Analgesics can be administered orally (p.o.), subcutaneously (s.c.), intramuscularly (i.m.), intravenously (i.v.), epidurally or subarachnoidally. The taken drug crosses many biological barriers in the organism finally reaching its site of action, which is the brain or the spinal cord. Anatomical and functional barriers rank among natural barriers. Anatomical barriers are built of lipids and water. A good example of this is methadone, a drug of high fat solubility, which depends to a large extent on glycoproteins.[5]

When administered subarachnoidally, opioids act in a somewhat another way at the dorsal horns. They spread over white matter of the spinal cord beneath which they reach appropriate receptors.

While selecting a narcotic analgesic other factors should be considered, such as drug metabolic pathway, kidney diseases, side effects, interactions between a drug and different types of receptors, and possibilities of non-opioid action (inhibition of serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake).

Classification of narcotic analgesics

According to their affinity to opioid receptors narcotic analgesics can be divided into agonists, antagonists or mixed agonist/antagonists. Another classification is based upon a way of production. By this criterion nar-

cotic analgesics can be categorised as synthetic, semi-synthetic, natural etc.

The World Health Organization (WHO) presents rules of pain management as recommendations for individual analgesics based on type of pain, its intensity and pharmacological effect of drug. The main criterion for choice of analgesic from a specific step of the pain ladder is pain intensity.[6] The schema placed below represents the analgesic ladder.

Step 1. Mild pain: Non-opioid analgesic + Optional adjuvant If pain persists or increases, go to step 2.

Step 2. Moderate pain: Weak opioid +Non-opioid analgesic + Optional adjuvant If pain persists or increases, go to step 3.

Step 3. Severe pain: Strong opioid +Non-opioid analgesic+ Optional adjuvant Freedom from pain.

The presented ladder consists of three steps:

First step drugs are non-opioid analgesics and additionally adjuvants. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, which inhibit synthesis of prostaglandins, paracetamol and metamizole are classified as non-opioid analgesics. Those drugs are recommended when a patient quantifies his pain level as 1-4 points on the visual analogue scale (VAS).

Second step drugs are weak opioids which can be administered with non-opioid analgesics. Weak opioids are codeine, tramadol and dihydrocodeine.

Third step drugs are strong opioids, such as morphine, oxycodone, fentanyl or methadone. It is acceptable to use strong opioids with non-opioid analgesics and co-analgesics. Third step drugs are administered when a patient's pain level is more than 6 points on the numeric rating scale (NRS).[7]

The WHO recommends administration of co-analgetics with every analgesic. The addition of adjuvants augments analgesic effect via inhibition of serotonin reuptake or reduction in sodium channels conduction. The co-analgesic include antidepressants, anticonvulsants and drugs with muscle relaxant properties.[6]

In clinical practice agonists are drugs affecting a definite receptor, causing its activation and eliciting a specific pharmacologic effect. Administration of pure agonists involves linear effect - each subsequent dose of

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drug potentiates analgesic effect. Morphine, codeine, fentanyl, pethidine and tramadol act as pure agonists. Buprenorphine numbers among partial agonists. Partial agonists joint a specific receptor, but their pharmacologic effect is limited to a large extent. What is more important drugs from the group of partial agonists elicit ceiling effect, which means they do not augment their pharmacologic effect with subsequent doses. Partial agonists can also induce abstinence symptoms due to their competitive action. Substance that reverses all effects induced by opiates is called antagonist. Antagonist reveals high affinity to a receptor, but simultaneously inhibits receptor activity. Opioid antagonists are naloxone and naltrexone.[8]

Nowadays measuring vital parameters and alleviation of pain, the fifth vital parameter, have been given high priority in treatment of sick patients. The commonest opioid analgesics are codeine, tramadol, buprenorphine, pethidine, methadone and fentanyl.

Codeine belongs to weak opioids. It is a derivative of morphine. Codeine has central antitussive effect and moderate analgesic and depressant effect. It absorbs easily from the digestive tract. Final stages of codeine metabolism occur in the liver. Codeine can be administered orally or rectally. It takes 45 minutes to reach its peak concentration in blood after oral administration. Codeine half-life amounts to 3 to 4 hours. Codeine daily recommended dose should not exceed 500 mg. Indications for codeine administration are persistent cough and moderate or great pain. Main adverse effects involve nausea and vomiting, and rarely pain in the upper abdomen and cramps. Codeine given in therapeutic doses does not result in respiratory depression and drug addiction. Codeine is contraindicated in unconscious patients.[8]

Tramadol is a weak opioid that does not only affect central opioid receptors, but also inhibits serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake, which augments its analgesic effect. It reaches maximal concentration in the body in 2 hours after administration. Tramadol half-life amounts to 4,5 hours. Analgesic effect starts 15-30 minutes after administration and lasts 3-4 hours. In case of persistent pain it is recommended to keep the concentration of the drug in a steady state. Tramadol daily recommended dose should not exceed 400 mg. Tramadol is used

in management of acute traumatic or postoperative pain. Adverse effects involve nausea, vomiting, sometimes mild neurological disorders, but they abate after several days. It is important to decrease a dose of the drug while changing a way of administration. Tramadol is distinguished by low potency for triggering drug dependency.[8, 9]

Buprenorphine has partial affinity for mu opioid receptor. It acts as an agonist with properties of antagonist. Such pharmacodynamic characteristics result in lack of augmentation of analgesic effect with increasing drug doses. Buprenorphine does not lead to respiratory depression. Compared with morphine, action of buprenorphine is 30 times more potent and lasts several hours longer. Buprenorphine can easily penetrate mucous membranes of the oral cavity, therefore it may be administered as sublingual pills. Buprenorphine also occurs in the form of transdermal patches with controlled liberation of the drug. It is possible to administer buprenorphine with other opioids which is a unique quality among the opioids. Apart from nausea and vomiting, adverse effects involve increased somnolence.[8]

Pethidine is a morphine derivative. It is a potent analgesic. It acts as an agonist of opioid receptors. In comparison with morphine, the analgesic strength of pethidine is significantly lower. Pethidine causes depression of the cardiovascular system and relaxation of smooth muscles. When administered intramuscularly, the drug absorbs rapidly and its pharmacologic action begins as early as in 15 minutes. Pethidine half-life amounts to 4-6 hours. Clinical indications for using pethidine are chronic pains of high intensity, pains accompanying renal or bile colic. Adverse effects include respiratory distress and Quincke's oedema due to liberation of histamine.[8]

Methadone is a synthetic agonist of opioid receptors and yet it acts as an agonist of NMDA receptors and inhibits norepinephrine and serotonin reuptake in the brain. Chemical structure of this compound permits its rapid action. Methadone half-life amounts to 8 up to more than 120 hours. Analgesic effect lasts 6-12 hours. A disproportion between methadone half-life and duration of its analgesic effect may result in accumulation during repeated methadone administration. Patient should be diligently monitored during administration of methadone

paying special attention to neurological disturbances. Methadone is metabolised in the liver, and eliminated in 60% by the digestive tract and in 20% by kidneys. The drug may be recommended to patients with renal failure. Methadone cannot be used by pregnant women and breastfeeding mothers.[9]

Fentanyl is one of the strong opioids. It belongs to the group of pure agonists of mu opioid receptor. Analgesic effect of fentanyl is 100 more potent than morphine, which means that 0,1 mg of fentanyl corresponds to analgesic effect of 10 mg of morphine. It results from chemical structure of fentanyl. The drug is more lipophilic than morphine and penetrates with ease the blood-brain barrier. Fentanyl found application in treatment of acute pain, including postoperative pain. Fentanyl is frequently administered intravenously or intramuscularly. After intravenous administration fentanyl acts as early as after 2 minutes, but its duration lasts only 30 minutes. Final stages of fentanyl metabolism occur in the liver, the drug is eliminated in the form of inactive metabolite. Similarly as other drugs, fentanyl is not deprived of adverse effects, which include nausea, vomiting, respiratory depression or skeletal muscle rigidity.[10]

Naloxone and naltrexone are rated as antagonists of opioid receptors. Naloxone is a pure antagonist. It reverses the action of agonists of opioid receptors. It is used as a specific antidote. Naloxone reverses adverse effects of opioid administration - respiratory depression and coma. Naloxone does not exert its own pharmacological effect, it does not influence drug tolerance and drug addiction. The pharmacological effect of antidote in large measure depends on a dose and quality of previously administered opioid. After intravenous administration of naloxone effect starts as early as in 30 seconds. Final stages of naloxone metabolism take place in the liver. Naloxone can cross the placental barrier. Indications for naloxone administration include opioid overdose, differentiation of types of coma and opioid poisoning, and respiratory depression. Naloxone can reverse analgesia in patients after surgical procedure. Naltrexone acts in a similar way, but there are completely different recommendations for its use. The drug found application in treatment of alcohol dependence since it decreases the need for drinking alcohol in the period of sobriety.

Through its pharmacological effect naltrexone did not find application in emergency medicine.[9,10]

Opioids application

Narcotic analgesics have wide application in modern medicine. They are used in anaesthesia with the aim of relieving the pain caused by surgical procedures. In these situations strong agonists of mu opioid receptors are mainly used. What is interesting in the 1970s extremely high doses of morphine were administered during cardiosurgical procedures. With the passing of time morphine was replaced by a safer opioid - fentanyl.[11] Adverse effects of opioids, namely respiratory depression and thoracic muscles rigidity, do not present problems for a doctor or nurse specialised in anaesthesia. During a surgical procedure patency of the patient's airway is secured by tracheal intubation and effective artificial ventilation. If complications to opioids administration arise, such as coma or prolonged respiratory depression, naloxone, a specific antidote, can be used.

In emergency medicine severe pain is frequent indication for opioid analgesic administration as part of the accident and emergency department. These drugs may also be used for pain management after small surgical procedures. After intravenous opioid administration patient should be carefully monitored. Potential threat may arise suddenly and may become a life-threatening situation.[7,11]

Contraindications for opioids administration

Administration of any drug can provoke additional adverse effects in every disease entity. Taking the patient's medical history correctly is particularly important in pain management, especially when opioids are administered. At the beginning of treatment it is important to assess the patient's state of consciousness with the Glasgow Coma Scale. First contraindication against narcotic analgesics administration is a situation when a patient is unconscious and not ventilated artificially. In case of respiratory failure, when impaired gas exchange in lungs leads to hypoxaemia, the choice of another drug should also be considered. Opioids with central effect have influence on the spinal respiratory centre and can increase respiratory failure. Craniocerebral traumata

constitute another problem. Craniocerebral traumata are severe injuries which can cause an increase in intracranial pressure. During opioid administration a patient should be carefully examined and special attention must be paid to kidney or liver diseases due to the risk of cumulation of toxic drug metabolites caused by decreased drug elimination. Another contraindications for opioid administration include both alcohol and drug dependence. Opioids should not be administered to patients with psychiatric diseases since they may exacerbate symptoms of basic disease.[8]

Adverse effects of opioids

Narcotic analgesics became standard in acute and chronic pain management. Pharmacological properties of opioids, such as lack of ceiling effect or slight organ toxicity, enable their broad administration. Long-term opioid use may result in opioid addiction or pseudoaddiction.[8]

Tolerance with reference to opioid analgesics is the term that means decrease of analgesic effect during administration similar doses of drug. Author indicates that while analysing the lack of analgesic effect typical psychological problems, such as anxiety and depression, should be considered.[12]

Psychological dependence is defined differently. It is a condition when a patient has to take a particular drug to fulfil his psychological need. Patient takes irrational attitudes, he buys or steals the drug. Dependence is frequently attributed to drug addiction. Drug addiction seldom occurs in pain treatment.[12]

Acute poisoning is another potential risk caused by the use of morphine or its derivatives. Administration 60 mg of morphine have a toxic impact on the human organism. Lethal dose of morphine amounts to 120-200 mg. The commonest symptoms of morphine poisoning include miosis, hypoventilation, depression of central nervous system, nausea, vomiting and depression of arterial blood pressure. Diagnostic tests include blood and urine sampling with the aim of morphine detection. Additionally respiratory pattern and heart rate should be monitored. Treatment of morphine poisoning is symptom-relieving. As soon as possible naloxone, a specific antidote, should be administered.

When adverse effects occur, a patient should be carefully monitored. Special attention should be paid to possible interactions between opioids and another drugs. Drugs that can affect opioid metabolism and increase the risk of occurring adverse effects of opioids number antidepressants, corticosteroids and benzodiazepines. Anna Orońska claims that intravenous administration of narcotic analgesics can lead to smaller retention of their toxic metabolites than during oral administration.[13]

Main adverse effects concerning the digestive tract include nausea and vomiting. Increased concentration of morphine metabolites in blood during renal failure favours the occurrence of these effects. Metoclopramid is a drug of choice used in case of the occurrence of gastrointestinal adverse effects. Patient frequently can report the feeling of dryness in his mouth, which may be considered as deep discomfort.[13]

Neurological disorders are the next group of adverse effects. They include delirium, myoclonic twitches and drowsiness. What is interesting a metabolite of pethidine reveals the highest neurotoxicity. Pethidine is not recommended in treatment of chronic pain. Hallucinations and delirium can appear during opioid administration or during increasing the doses of opioid. Neuroleptics may be used to prevent them.[13]

While administering morphine to the injured, he should be informed about possible drowsiness or apathy. These symptoms may not arouse reservations of patients in good state. But patients with severe injuries should have their airway secured and should be ventilated artificially. Possibility of the occurrence of myoclonic twitches should be explained to the patient. Muscle rigidity is possible to occur during intravenous administration of opioids. In case of convulsions, patient should be secured and should receive benzodiazepines.[14]

Situation is more complicated when adverse effects concern the respiratory tract. The severest complication of opioid therapy is respiratory depression. It is proved that in case of acute pain treatment the risk of respiratory depression decreases with alleviation of pain.[15]

Symptoms of respiratory depression involve increased partial pressure of carbon dioxide in arterial blood and decreased respiratory rate to 8 breaths per minute. During a morphine overdose at first neurological disorders

occur and they result in respiratory depression. Naloxone is a drug that reverses respiratory depression. The recommended dose of naloxone is 0,4 mg.

Tachycardia is a symptom from the side of cardiovascular system. It may appear as a consequence of rapid administration of opioid drug.

Pruritus is a frequent adverse effect occurring during subcutaneous injection of opioids. It appears at 90% of patients as a mild inflammatory reaction. To prevent pruritus, continuous morphine infusion is recommended.[15]

Summary

In the 21st century no man should feel pain and anxiety. Pain is always a subjective sensation and it should be born in mind while choosing a suitable analgesic. No type of pain should be disregarded by a doctor, nurse or rescue team. Medicine has at its disposal a complete arsenal of analgesics. Their administration should involve a desired clinical effect. Unfortunately the occurrence of adverse effects is frequently observed during opioid treatment. Administration of narcotic drugs requires careful monitoring of patient's vital signs and condition of patient's organs. The occurrence of respiratory depression is the most serious and constitutes a direct threat to patient's life. It results in respiratory failure and may lead to death as a consequence. In case of respiratory depression treatment should aim at removing symptoms and naloxone should be administered routinely.

References

1. Buczek W., Danysz A., Kompendium farmakologii i farmakoterapii, Wyd. Elsevier Urban & Partner, Wrocław, 2008; 202-210.
2. Pawłowski M., Chemia leków. Podręcznik dla studentów farmacji i farmaceutów, w: Zając A., Gorczyca M., (red), Wyd. Lekarskie PZWL, Warszawa, 2013; 175-189
3. Krajnik M., Żylicz Z., Mechanizm działania przeciwbólowy opioidów, „Polska Medycyna Paliatywna”, 2003; nr 3, vol 3, 111-118
4. Filipczak-Bryniarska I., Bryniarski K., Woron J., Wordliczek J., Mechanizm przewodzenia bólu. Rola układu odpornościowego w regulacji odczuwania bólu, „Anestezjologia i Ratownictwo”, 2010; nr 4, 500-509
5. Dobrogowski J., Przeklasa-Muszyńska A., Woron J., Wordliczek J., Zasady kojarzenia leków w terapii bólu, „Medycyna Paliatywna w Praktyce”, 2007; nr 1 vol 1, 6-15
6. Antosik-Wójcicka A., Bodzak-Opolska G., Leki przeciwbólowe w populacji ludzi po 65. roku życia, „Psychiatria”, 2013; nr 3 ton 10, 139-143.
7. Dobrogowski J., Golec A., Kobylarz K., Sedlak K., Wordliczek J., Medycyna bólu, w: Dobrogowski J., Wordliczek J. (red.), Wyd. Lekarskie PZWL, Warszawa, 2004; 19-33, 72-87, 88-98, 128-135, 578-581.
8. Koszewski W., Leczenie bólu w różnych schorzeniach, w: Koszewski W., (red), Warszawa, 2009; Wyd. Termedia.
9. Kotlińska-Lemieszek A., Zaporowska-Stachowiak I., Bobkiewicz-Kozłowska T., Leki przeciwbólowe – nowe spojrzenie na interakcje, „Terapia”, 2012; nr 10, 65-71
10. Baza leków, Medycyna Praktyczna dla Lekarzy, [online]
11. Dobrogowski J., Wordliczek J., Zajączkowska R., Zastosowanie leków opioidowych w leczeniu bólu, „Wszechświat”, 2013; nr 1-3, ton 114, 10-11
12. Adamczyk A., Krajnik M., Żylicz Z., Jak działają opioidy w duszność, „Medycyna Paliatywna”, 2003; nr 3, 183-190.
13. De Walden-Gałuszko K., Psychologiczne aspekty bólu i jego leczenia, „Medycyna Paliatywna w Praktyce”, 2007; nr 1, vol 2, 66-70
14. Orońska A., Działania niepożądane opioidów, „Medycyna Paliatywna”, 2008; nr 2, vol 4, 155-164
15. Lisowska B., Rell-Bakalarska M., Rutkowska-Sak L., Zastosowanie opioidów w leczeniu bólu w chorobach reumatycznych, „Reumatologia”, 2007; nr 45, vol 1, 46-49

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